

ELIXIR-Metabolomics Community

Fluxomics Training School 2021

October 4th-8th (virtual)

Day 1. Monday, October 4

08:45 - 09:00 Welcoming remarks

- 09:00 - 09:50** Introduction to basic metabolomics (Claire O'Donovan, EBI)
- 10:00 - 10:50** Systems biology from genomics to metabolomics, an overview (Adam Amara, IARC)
- 11:00 - 11:50** Experimental techniques in metabolomics & fluxomics (Mass Spectrometry/NMR) (Reza Salek, IARC)

12:10 - 13:00 Lunch Break

- 13:00 - 13:50** Introduction to Metabolomics Resources (Claire O'Donovan, EBI)
- 14:00 - 14:50** Rhea Knowledgebase (Venkatesh Muthukrishnan & Parit Bansal, SIB)
- 15:00 - 15:50** Microbial growth modelling, stoichiometric models and reconciliation of metabolites (Marco Pagni, SIB)

16:00 - 16:30 Team project assignments

16:45 - 19:30 Welcome Reception and Poster session

Day 2. Tuesday, October 5

- 09:00 - 09:50** Basic Mathematical Concepts for Fluxomics (Effrosyni Karakitsou & Marilena Pantziri, FORTH/ICE-HT)
- 10:00 - 10:50** Linear and Non Linear Programming (Effrosyni Karakitsou, Marilena Pantziri & Maria Klapa, FORTH/ICE-HT)
- 10:55 - 11:40** Observability & Data Reconciliation Analysis (Maria Klapa, FORTH/ICE-HT)
- 11:50 - 12:40** SBML (Marta Cascante, UB)

12:40 - 13:00 Lunch Break

- 13:30 - 14:20** Introduction to Programming with MATLAB (Shubo Chakrabarti, MATLAB)
- 14:30 - 15:20** Standardization of metabolic reaction databases and use in fluxomics (Egon Willighagen, UM)
- 15:30 - 16:20** How to use Galaxy in fluxomics (Yann Guitton, Oniris Nantes)

16:30 - 17:00 Discussion Session

Day 3. Wednesday, October 6

- 09:00 - 09:50** Introduction to fluxomics - stoichiometric modelling - Basic concepts (Marta Cascante, UB)

- 10:00 - 10:50** Hands-on exercises on COPASI-steady state and flux control (Pedro de Atauri, Marta Cascante, UB)
- 11:00 - 11:50** Hands-on exercises on COPASI-steady state and flux control (Pedro de Atauri, Marta Cascante, UB)
- 12:00 - 13:00** **Lunch Break**
- 13:00 - 13:50** Basic ^{13}C fluxomics concepts (Jean-Charles Portais, INSA)
- 14:00 - 14:50** ^{13}C -fluxomics in practice: from cultivation to sampling (Edern Cahoreau, INSA)
- 15:00 - 15:50** ^{13}C -fluxomics in practice: from samples to data (Florian Bellvert & Edern Cahoreau, INSA)
- 15:20 - 15:50** Evaluation & Case studies - Cultivation, Sampling and analyses (Cécilia Berges & Noémie Butin, INSA)
- 16:00 - 16:50** (1) Metabolomics Standards & Fluxomics - (2) Sharing SIRM / Fluxomics Data: accommodating annotation requirements in EMBL MetaboLights and ISA format (Philippe Rocca-Serra, UOXF & Claire O'Donovan, EBI)
- 17:00 - 17:30** Discussion session

Day 4. Thursday, October 7

- 09:00 - 09:20** Data quality (Florian Bellvert, INSA)
- 09:20 - 10:40** Flux calculations - Part 1 (Pierre Millard, INSA)
- 10:50 - 11:20** Flux calculations - Part 2 (Pierre Millard, INSA)
- 11:20 - 12:00** Evaluation & Case studies - Flux calculation (Cécilia Berges & Noémie Butin, INSA)

12:00 - 13:00 Lunch Break - Office hours

- 13:00 - 13:50** Integration of Genome-Scale Metabolic Modeling with C_{13} -fluxomics (Ronan Fleming, LEI)
- 14:00 - 14:50** COBRA 3.0 - Hands on exercises (Ronan Fleming, LEI)
- 15:00 - 15:50** Panel Discussion: Integration of Genome-Scale Metabolic Modeling with C_{13} -fluxomics & The challenge of Metabolic Model Standardization (Marilena Pantziri, Maria Klapa, Marco Pagni, Ronan Fleming)

16:00 – 17:00 Keynote Lecture by Gregory Stephanopoulos, MIT

17:15 – 18:00 Night at the Museum: Virtual Tour of the Archaeological Museum of Patras, Greece

Day 5. Friday, October 8

- 10:00 – 10:50** Integration of fluxomics with other - OMICS data: case studies, opportunities, challenges (Effrosyni Karakitsou, FORTH/ICE-HT)
- 11:00 – 11:50** Microbial Biotechnology Applications (Vitor Martins dos Santos & Maria Suarez, WUR)

12:00 - 13:00 Lunch Break

- 13:00 - 14:20** Biomedical applications (Andrew Lane & Teresa Fan, UKY)

- 14:30 - 16:30** Presentations of Team Projects

16:30 - 17:00 Closing Remarks